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MODERN APPROACHES AND METHODS OF TEACHING GRAMMAR IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the fundamental role of grammar in the process of teaching English as a foreign language. The author examines the concept of "grammar" from both intuitive and constructed perspectives, highlighting its importance as a tool for understanding the human mind and developing communication skills. The paper outlines the criteria for selecting grammar material for school syllabuses, such as frequency and polysemy. A comparative analysis of traditional and modern teaching methodologies is provided, including the Grammar-Translation Method, the Direct Method, and the Audio-lingual Method. Special attention is given to interactive, game-based technologies, such as word puzzles and Bingo, as effective means of increasing student motivation and engagement. The article concludes that a communicative approach to grammar is essential for achieving language proficiency in primary and secondary education.*

Keywords: *English language teaching, grammar instruction, communicative approach, Grammar-Translation Method, Direct Method, primary school education, language acquisition, pedagogical techniques, game-based learning, interactive methods, linguistic skills.*

Introduction

Language is a tool that helps people communicate, it enables them to express their thoughts, opinions, feelings and points of view, in order to exchange information, talk about experiences, likes and dislikes, to explore similarities and differences. There is no efficient and successful language learning without having good knowledge of grammar structures and their functions in language. Over the last few decades, a great debate has taken place among theorists as to what is the role of grammar. The word grammar in the usual narrow sense of the term evokes rather negative images such as rules, drills, exams and red marks on paper. In its broadest sense grammar is viewed as dependent upon the meanings a structure is carrying, not just the rules. Grammar is an integral part of any language teaching process. Some consider grammar as a science of language system while others consider it just a list of rules to learn and memorize in order to be able to speak and write correctly. Certain notions and approaches to teaching languages started to emerge that neglect the role of grammar in acquiring a second language. These sorts of notions were based on the grounds that children didn't have to learn grammar to pick up their first language [1,13].

These notions, however, were proven later on impractical as grammar plays an replace able role in breaking down the language for kids and facilitating it to adults. This research is an attempt to highlight the vitality of grammar in teaching and acquiring a second language. The role grammar plays can take many dimensions. Some of the roles discussed in this paper are its ability to convey unambiguous meaning, having the capacity to create an infinite set of sentences and a substantial enabling skill. Additionally, grammar forms an important subject in almost all the syllabuses all around the world. Be it English grammar or any other grammar, be it a native or a bilingual, a person can't write or speak eloquently bereft of this key factor.

Main part. The teaching of grammar has always been a central aspect of foreign language teaching. Grammar is important because it is the language that makes it possible for us to talk about language. Grammar names the types of words and word groups that make up sentences not only in English, but in any language. As human beings, we can put sentences together even as children. But to be able to talk about how sentences are built, about the types of words and word groups that make

up sentences - that is knowledge of grammar. And knowledge of grammar offers a window into the human mind and into our amazingly complex mental capacity. Teaching grammar is a central concern in English language teaching [2,5].

Before speaking about the selection of grammar material it is necessary to consider the concept "grammar", i.e., what it meant by "grammar". By grammar one can mean adequate comprehension and correct usage of words in the act of communication, that is, intuitive knowledge of the grammar of the language. It is a set of reflexes enabling a person to communicate with his associates. Such knowledge is acquired by a child in the mother tongue before he goes to schools.

This "grammar" functions without the individual's awareness of technical nomenclature; in other words, he has no idea of the system of the language, and to use all the word-endings for singular and plural, for tense, and all the other grammar rules without special grammar lessons only due to the abundance of ausing and speaking. His young mind grasps the facts and "makes simple grammar rules" for arranging the words to express carious thoughts and feelings. This is true because sometimes little children make mistakes by using a common rule for words to which that rule cannot be applied. For example, a little English child might be heard to say Two mans comed instead of Two men come, because the child is using the plural "s" rule for man to which the rule does not apply, and the past tense ed rule for come which does not obey the ordinary rule for the past tense formation.

By "grammar" we also mean the system of the language, the discovery and description of the nature of language itself. It is not a natural grammar, but a constructed one. There are several constructed grammars: traditional, structural, and transformational grammars. Traditional grammar studies the forms of words (morphology) and how they are put together in sentences (syntax); structural grammar studies structures of various levels of the language (morpheme level) and syntactic level; transformational grammar studies basic structures and transformation rules [3, 52].

What we need is simplest and shortest grammar that meets the requirements of the school syllabus in foreign languages. This grammar must be simple enough to be grasped and held by any pupil. We cannot say that this problem has been solved. Since graduates are expected to acquire language proficiency in aural comprehension, speaking and reading grammar material should be selected for the purpose. There exist principles of selecting grammar material both for teaching speaking knowledge (active minimum) and for teaching reading knowledge (passive minimum), the main one is the principle of frequency, i.e., how frequently this or that grammar item occurs. For example, the Present Simple (Indefinite) is frequently used both in conversation and in various texts. Therefore it should be included in the grammar minimum. For selecting grammar material for reading the principle of polysemia, for instance, is of great importance. Pupils should be taught to distinguish such grammar items which serve to express different meanings. For example, -s (es). The content of grammar teaching is disputable among teachers and methodologists, and there are various approaches to the problem, pupils should, whatever the content of the course, assimilate the ways of fitting words together to form sentences and be able to easily recognize grammar forms and structures while hearing and reading, to reproduce phrases and sentences stored up in their memory and say or write sentences of their own, using grammar items appropriate to the situation.

Grammar is central to the teaching and learning of languages. It is also one of the more difficult aspects of language to teach well.

Many people, including language teachers, hear the word "grammar" and think of a fixed set of word forms and rules of usage. They associate "good" grammar with the prestige forms of the language, such as those used in writing and in formal oral presentations, and "bad" or "no" grammar with the language used in everyday conversation or used by speakers of no prestige forms.

Language teachers who adopt this definition focus on grammar as a set of forms and rules. They teach grammar by explaining the forms and rules and then drilling students on them. This results in bored, disaffected students who can produce correct forms on exercises and tests, but consistently make errors when they try to use the language in context.

Teaching grammar is an essential part of school education or adult learning. Without good grammar, spoken or written words lose much of their meaning and most of their value. Grammar

is a very important thing to get right, and teachers should take extra care to impart proper grammar to all their students. Sadly, grammar is often seen as a difficult and boring subject and one popular method of teaching is to just repeat the correct grammar for a certain situation over and over until it is memorised and able to be repeated, like a parrot. This is dull for both teachers and students, and often only results in the students being able to repeat what they have learned, rather than resulting in a complete understanding that can be applied to all situations [4,15].

Word puzzles are a useful and interactive method whereby students can learn all sorts of important parts of English grammar. They can be used to encourage students to identify and understand various parts of a sentence; grammatical concepts like synonyms, tenses and conjugations; or incorrectly used grammar. Word puzzles such as crosswords are easily modified to suit all age and skill levels and introduce an element of fun competition into the learning process, so they can be invaluable in forging a full and lasting understanding of English grammar.

Another game-based method of teaching grammar that you could use in teaching your students is Bingo. The game of Bingo is based on people marking off spaces on their card until they fill in a row or column fully. In normal Bingo these are numbers, drawn at random from a pool. In grammar lesson Bingo, they could be pronouns, verbs, nouns, sentence structure, antonyms, and so on – students could use the daily newspaper and attempt to find correct examples of these grammatical concepts faster than each other, thereby “winning” the game – and learning in the process! Short and fun grammar exercises like this can be included on a regular basis during your lessons to keep correct grammar usage fresh your students’ minds and improve their recall of the topics at hand. *Advanced English Grammar* is an online lesson plan featuring quizzes and lectures to help you teach your students all the elements of good grammar. One particularly useful lesson could be spent on highlighting common mistakes that people make, and incidences of grammar not fitting the expected pattern. By teaching your students what is incorrect in this way, you can help them to avoid making these common mistakes. Turning it into a funny or amusing session of picking out subtle mistakes or ways that poor grammar has led a normal sentence to become ambiguous, funny or wrong can really help make your lesson very memorable, and one lesson of showing students what is wrong can often be more valuable than several lessons of trying to teach what is right.

In summation, all education depends on a foundation of good grammar. If students cannot understand grammar, they will struggle to read, write or speak clearly in any other area of education, from maths and science to history or geography. Good language is the base on which all other education has to stand. Teachers can use a variety of ways to make their grammar lessons memorable and enjoyable for students. Students who enjoy their lessons will pay closer attention, and you will then have an easier time while teaching. This is why great lessons are important for everyone involved, and why you should take the time to ensure you are teaching grammar in the best and most engaging way for the skill level and requirements of your individual students.

The grammatical systems of Russian and English are fundamentally different. English is an analytical language, in which grammatical meaning is largely expressed through the use of additional words and by changes in word order. Russian is a synthetic language, in which the majority of grammatical forms are created through changes in the structure of words, by means of a developed system of prefixes, suffixes and ending. No one knows exactly how people learn languages although a great deal of research has been done into the subject [5,6].

Many methods have been proposed for the teaching of foreign language. And they have met with varying degrees of success and failure.

We should know that the method by which children are taught must have some effect on their motivation. If they find it deadly boring they will probably become de-motivated, whereas if they have confidence in the method they will find it motivating. Child learners differ from adult learners in many ways. Children are curious, their attention is of a shorter duration, they are quite differently motivated in, and their interests are less specialized. They need frequent of activity; they need

activities which are exciting and stimulating their curiosity; they need to be involved in something active.

We shall examine such methods as “The Grammar - Translation Method”, “The Direct Method”, “The Audio-lingual Method”. And we pay attention to the teaching grammar of the foreign language. We shall comment those methods, which have had a long history.

a) The Grammar Translation method

This method was widely used in teaching the classics, namely Latin, and it was transferred to the teaching of modern languages when they were introduced into schools. In the grammar-translation mode, the books begin with definitions of the parts of speech, declensions, conjugations, rules to be memorized, examples illustrating the rules, and exceptions. Often each unit has a paragraph to be translated into the target language and one to be translated into native one. These paragraphs illustrate the grammar rules studied in the unit. The student is expected to apply the rules on his own. This involves a complicated mental manipulation of the conjugations and declensions in the order memorized, down to the form that might fit the translation. As a result, students are unable to use the language, and they sometimes develop an inferiority complex about languages in general. Exceptionally bright and diligent students do learn languages by this method, or in spite of it, but they would learn with any method [6, 8].

We list the major characteristics of Grammar Translation.

- Classes are taught in the mother tongue, with little active use of the target language.
- Much vocabulary is taught in the form of lists of isolated words.
- Long elaborate explanations of the intricacies of grammar are given.
- Grammar provides the rules for putting words together, and instruction often focuses on the form and inflection of word.
- Reading of difficult classical texts is begun early.
- Little attention is paid to the content of texts, which are treated as exercises in grammatical analysis.
- Often the only drills are exercises in translating disconnected sentences from the target language into the mother tongue.
- Little or no attention is given to pronunciation.

The grammar-translation method is largely discredited today. With greater interest in modern languages for communication the inadequacy of grammar-translation methods became evident.

b) The Direct Method

The Direct Method appeared as a reaction against the grammar-translation method. There was a movement in Europe that emphasized language learning by direct contact with the foreign language in meaningful situations. This movement resulted in various individual methods with various names, such as new method, natural method, and even oral method, but they can all be referred to as direct methods or the direct method. In addition to emphasizing direct contact with the foreign language, the direct method usually deemphasized or eliminated translation and the memorization of conjugations, declensions, and rules, and in some cases it introduced phonetics and phonetic transcription.

The direct method assumed that learning a foreign language is the same as learning the mother tongue, that is, that exposing the student directly to the foreign language impresses it perfectly upon his mind. This is true only up to a point, since the psychology of learning a second language differs from that of learning the first. The child is forced to learn the first language because he has no other effective way to express his wants. In learning a second language this compulsion is largely missing, since the student knows that he can communicate through his native language when necessary [7, 52].

The basic premise of Direct Method was that second language learning should be more like first language learning: lots of active oral interaction, spontaneous use of the language, no translation between first and second languages, and little or no analysis of grammatical rules. We can summarize the principles of the Direct.

Method:

- Classroom instruction was conducted exclusively in the target language.
- Only everyday vocabulary and sentences were taught.
- Oral communication skills were built up in a carefully graded progression organized around question-and-answer exchanges between teachers and student in small, intensive classes.
- Grammar was taught inductively, i.e. the learner may discover the rules of grammar for himself after he has become acquainted with many examples.
- New teaching points were introduced orally.
- Concrete vocabulary was taught through demonstration, objects, and pictures; abstract vocabulary was taught by association of ideas.
- Both speech and listening comprehension were taught.
- Correct pronunciation and grammar were emphasized.

c) The Audiolingual Method

The Audiolingual Method (It is also called Mimicry-memorization method) was the method developed in the Intensive Language Program. It was successful because of high motivation, intensive practice, small classes, and good models, in addition to linguistically sophisticated descriptions of the foreign language and its grammar [8,23].

Grammar is taught essentially as follows: Some basic sentences are memorized by imitation. Their meaning is given in normal expressions in the native language, and the students are not expected to translate word for word. When the basic sentences have been overlearned (completely memorized so that the student can rattle them off without effort), the student reads fairly extensive descriptive grammar statements in his native language, with examples in the target language and native language equivalents. He then listens to further conversational sentences for practice in listening. Finally, practices the dialogues using the basic sentences and combinations of their parts. When he can, he varies the dialogues within the material he has already learned. The characteristics of ALM may be summed up in the following list:

- New material is presented in dialog form.
- There is dependence on mimicry, memorization of set phrases and overlearning.
- Structures are sequenced by means of contrastive analysis and taught one at a time.
- Structural patterns are taught using repetitive drills.
- There is a little or no grammatical explanation: grammar is taught by inductive analogy rather than deductive explanation.
- Vocabulary is strictly limited and learned in context.
- There is much use of tapes, language labs, and visual aids.
- Great importance is attached to pronunciation.
- very little use of the mother tongue by teachers is permitted.
- Successful responses are immediately reinforced.
- There is a great effort to get students to produce error-free utterances.
- There is a tendency to manipulate language and disregard content.

Each method is realized in techniques. By a technique we mean an individual way in doing something, in gaining a certain goal in teaching learning process. The method and techniques the teacher should use in teaching children of the primary school is the direct method, and various techniques which can develop pupils' listening comprehension and speaking. Pupils are given various exercises, connected with the situational use of words and sentence patterns.

Types of exercise for the assimilation of grammar

a) Recognition exercises

These exercises are the easiest type of exercises for pupils to perform. They observe the grammar item in structures (sentence patterns) when hearing or reading. Since pupils only observe the new grammar item the situations should be natural and communicative.

Listen to the sentences and raise your hands whenever you hear the verbs in the Past Simple.

Mike lives in Pushkin Street. I lived there last year. Ann gets up at 7 o'clock in the morning. She got up at half past seven yesterday.

It is desirable that sentences formed should concern real situations and facts.

Pupils listen to the teacher and raise their hands when they hear a verb in the Past Simple. The teacher can see whether each of his pupils has grasped the sentence.

Pupils should read the sentences and find the signals for the correct choice of the form. Since the necessary form is suggested in each sentence they should only recognize the one they need for a given context.

Recognition exercises are indispensable as pupils retain the grammar material through auditory and visual perception. Auditory and visual memory is at work.

b) Drill exercises

They are more completed as they require reproduction on the part of the pupils. In learning a foreign language drill exercises are indispensable. The learners cannot assimilate the material if they only hear and see it. They must reproduce it both in outer and inner speech. The more often they say it the better they assimilate the material. Though drill exercises are those in which pupils have only one difficulty to overcome, they should also be graded:

- Repetitive drill. Pupils pronounce the sentence pattern after the teacher, in imitation of the teacher, both individually and in unison.

Attention is drawn to the correct pronunciation of the sentence pattern as a sense unit, as a statement (sounds, stress, and melody).

- Substitution. Pupils substitute the words or phrases in a sentence pattern.

A pupil substitutes a phrase, the rest may say it in unison. Then they are invited to replace the word dancing with other words.

There is one more advantage in performing this type of exercises--pupils consolidate the grammar item without thinking about it. They think of the words, phrases, but not of the form itself, therefore, involuntary memory is at work.

- Completion

Pupils complete the sentences the teacher utters looking at the pictures he shows.

Attention should be given to the use of *is* in this exercise. The teacher should pronounce *Mike is ...* to prevent the typical mistake of the pupils (*Mike dressing*). This is essential structural element of the tense form of the Present Continuous; Russian-speaking pupils, however, do not feel any necessity to use it.

- Answering the teacher's questions

Drill exercises may be done both orally and in written form. Pupils perform oral exercises during the lesson and written ones at home. For example, they are told to write five or seven sentences on the model given.

During the next lesson the work done at home is checked orally. In this way pupils have practice in pronunciation while reading their own examples, and in auditing while listening to their classmates.

Results. During the practice in the state institution secondary school number 155 we carried out an experimental work the introduction of a variety of teaching methods of English grammar. We worked with 1th, 2th and 3th grades. For experimental work was chosen 3 "A" and 3 "B" classes. It must be noted that pupils have been learning English language three years, third classes once a week, therefore, the level of skills acquisition and skills is average. The classes are divided into 2 groups. In 3 "A" - 15 pupils at the first group and 14 at the second group and in the 3 "B" – 14 pupils in the first group and 14 pupils in second group. The 3 "A, B" classes are used the book "English 3" by «Алматыкітап». The children's ages ranged from 7-8 years to 9-10 years. Many of the children were bilingual; mainly ethnic Russian and the state - the Kazakh language; also had children speak the mother tongue of other nationalities. English have been under study.

At the first lesson, was given a test to determine the level of knowledge of English grammar. The results were positive. To determine which of the techniques is more effective was a comparative analysis in the third grades.

3 "A" we used the grammar translation method and drill exercises.

3 "B" we used the direct method and creative exercises.

TEST

1. Write translation the words

A Café - _____

A museum - _____

A hospital - _____

A park - _____

A theatre - _____

A bank - _____

2. Answer the questions.

1. Is there a historical museum in your city? _____

2. Are there any cafes in your city? _____

3. Put **Is** or **Are**.

1. _____ there London a beautiful city?

2. _____ there any museums in Astana?

3. _____ there a river in Astana?

4. _____ there any buildings in Astana?

4. Answer the questions.

a) What is the capital of Kazakhstan? - _____

b) What is the capital of Great Britain? - _____

c) What is the tower of Astana? - _____

d) What is the tower of London? - _____

5. Choose the right letter.

Cl__ck (a, o, e)

to__er (v, p, w)

C__pital (a, e, y)

sq__are (o, y, u)

Sc__ool (h, t, g)

c__ty (o, i, u)

Result of the first test – 3 “A”:

№	Surname and name	Mark
1	Aznabakieva Aziza	5
2	Akimov Temirlan	5
3	Bosakova Kamila	4
4	Bogdanov Ruslan	3
5	Djumagaliev Mihrat	3
6	Islamova Amira	4
7	Ismailova Dil'bar	3
8	Kamalova Mirana	4
9	Luchenko Mariya	5
10	Nurdinov Aziz	4

Figure 1

The average grade – 4
Result of the first test – 3 “B”:

№	Surname and name	Mark
1	Amirov Zafar	5
2	Asanov Alisher	3
3	Dautova Dilyara	3
4	Ilitskaya Nataliya	4
5	Ibrahimov Muhtar	4
6	Farminov Dil'murat	3
7	Kebirov Il'ham	4
8	Kirpechenko Vladimir	5
9	Lisichkina Alena	5
10	Nautiev Mirzan	3

Figure 2

The average grade – 4

3 “A” we used the grammar translation method and drill exercises.

To explain to the students (grammar) How to ask questions and briefly answer with there is/there are, I used the Grammar-Translation Method.

In the grammar-translation mode, the books begin with definitions of the parts of speech, declensions, conjugations, rules to be memorized, examples illustrating the rules, and exceptions. Often each unit has a paragraph to be translated into the target language and one to be translated into native one. These paragraphs illustrate the grammar rules studied in the unit. The student is expected to apply the rules on his own. This involves a complicated mental manipulation of the conjugations and declensions in the order memorized, down to the form that might fit the translation.

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- Little or no attention is given to pronunciation.

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For practicing new grammar topics we used drill exercises. Let’s repeat the rules how to ask questions with there is/there are. Давайте повторим правила как задавать вопросы с there is/there are. Repeat after me – Are there any towers in Astana ? – Yes, there is, а как скажем нет,нету? No, there aren’t. Is there the Khan Shatyr in London? – No, there isn’t.

On the whiteboard displays the words, and written on the blackboard drawing example of the issue . You must replace the underlined word by taking the word that is written on the whiteboard . Be careful where you specify there is, where there are. We perform this exercise in writing form in your notebooks. And answer these questions in a positive and negative form.

Is there museum in your city?

Are the any museums in your city?

A museums a cafés

a theatre a square

a hospitals a bank

3 “B” we used the direct method and creative exercises.

The Direct Method appeared as a reaction against the grammar-translation method.

This movement resulted in various individual methods with various names, such as new method, natural method, and even oral method, but they can all be referred to as direct methods or the direct method. In addition to emphasizing direct contact with the foreign language, the direct method usually deemphasized or eliminated translation and the memorization of conjugations, declensions, and rules, and in some cases it introduced phonetics and phonetic transcription.

The basic premise of Direct Method was that second language learning should be more like first language learning: lots of active oral interaction, spontaneous use of the language, no translation between first and second languages, and little or no analysis of grammatical rules. We can summarize the principles of the Direct Method:

- Classroom instruction was conducted exclusively in the target language.

Conclusion. Having analyzed the literature on methods of teaching a foreign language, it can be concluded that teaching grammar at school should occupy a leading position, as grammatical skill is one of the components of speaking. The acquisition of language as a means of communication is the aim of learning. The most common approach to the teaching of grammatical aspects of the English language is the communicative approach [3, 15]. Teachers should use a variety of ways to make their grammar lessons memorable and enjoyable, ensuring that grammar is taught in the most engaging

way for the skill level of individual students [9]. The mastering of grammar is impossible without learning grammatical structures, grammatical meaning of the structure, as well as the formation of grammatical skill. To increase students' interest in learning such a complex language as the grammar, first of all, you need to put in front of him, i.e. in front of the teacher, clear objectives. Students need to know and understand why they do a particular task or learn certain rules. The next thing to consider is the variety of tasks. All tasks that are given to students should be carefully and thoughtfully selected by the teacher. No less important in the grammar is clarity. Students must have a good example or a rule, which is then quickly absorbed students. Games must also be present in the classroom. So-called games help children to relax, and with each job may have a clear goal. When using didactic games, training of grammatical structures and grammatical skills that is of great practical importance.

In order to understand a language and express oneself correctly one must assimilate the grammar mechanism of a language. Children need grammar to be able to speak, and write in the target language. Our aim is to form grammar skills and prevent children from making grammar mistakes in their speech. The aim of foreign languages in primary schools is to develop pupils' skills in order to understand speech and participate in conversation.

The method and techniques the teacher should use in teaching children of primary school is the direct method and various techniques which can develop pupils' listening comprehension and speaking.

We have such a conclusion that the forming of grammar skills depends on training. Training is of great importance to realize the grammar item. We must use a lot of training exercises for the assimilation of grammar. We should provide the motivation of learn English, encourage children to communicate and remember that the correction of errors in the early stages of a language course may foster the following negative aspects:

- children lose confidence when they have fear of making grammar mistakes
- children become reluctant to take risks: they only say the information they know they can say

We should realize the importance of training exercises and the role of the individual approach to teaching the children. Besides, the teacher must have a clear idea of the grammar of the language, its structure and usage; everything he teaches must be based on it; he should always be conscious of introducing or practicing some point of grammar.

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